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Exploring Teacher Awareness and Challenges in Managing Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) Behaviors in Inclusive Education Settings

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Abstract: This study examines the level of awareness among special education and general education teachers regarding the behaviors of children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and explores the relationship between this awareness and two key demographic factors: years of experience and attendance at autism-related seminars and trainings. The results indicate a moderate level of awareness among the respondents, but no significant correlation was found between years of teaching experience and awareness levels. However, a significant positive correlation was observed between the number of seminars attended and the level of awareness, highlighting the critical role of professional development. Teachers reported several challenges, including a lack of support from parents and school administration, insufficient instructional materials, and difficulties managing inclusive classrooms. The findings underscore the importance of continuous training and institutional support to enhance teachers' ability to effectively support children with ASD in inclusive education settings.

Keywords: Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), teacher awareness, special education, general education, inclusive education

Introduction

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by challenges in social communication and behavior. The "spectrum" nature of ASD refers to the wide variability in symptoms and severity observed among individuals (Jarbou et al., 2021). Current estimates indicate a global increase in ASD prevalence, with approximately 1 in 54 children diagnosed with ASD in the United States (Maenner et al., 2020). The increasing number of children diagnosed with ASD has resulted in a growing population of students with ASD in schools, where the challenges they face often include

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difficulties in processing sensory input, maintaining focus, and engaging in social interactions (Jones et al., 2020). These difficulties can have significant impacts on learning outcomes and overall school participation (Hodges et al., 2019). For instance, students with ASD often face challenges navigating complex social environments, which may contribute to emotional distress and behavioral issues (Zainal & Magiati, 2019). Moreover, the heterogeneity of ASD symptoms, including cognitive and behavioral differences, makes the provision of appropriate support in educational settings a critical yet complex issue (Hidalgo et al., 2021). Public and private schools vary in the level of support they provide, with public schools often offering more resource

Special education and general education teachers share the responsibility of fostering inclusive environments that cater to the diverse needs of students, including those with ASD. General education teachers are tasked with delivering curriculum content while managing a classroom, whereas special education teachers often focus on individualized instruction and behavioral interventions for students with special needs (Azeem et al., 2019). However, the effectiveness of both roles depends heavily on teachers' understanding and awareness of ASD-related behaviors, including how to respond to sensory sensitivities and social communication challenges (Jones et al., 2020). A lack of training and awareness can result in frustration, both for the student and teacher, and may lead to missed opportunities for effective intervention (Khalil et al., 2020). Teachers with adequate training are more likely to recognize the unique behavioral patterns of children with ASD, which allows them to implement classroom strategies that enhance learning and social interactions (Almuaigel & Almuaigel, 2019). Educators also play a key role in identifying the early signs of ASD and working with specialists to create personalized learning plans (Datta et al., 2023). Therefore, teacher awareness and proper training are critical for managing ASD-related behaviors in the classroom environment (Harris et al., 2020).

Research consistently highlights gaps in teacher awareness and understanding of the behaviors associated with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). For instance, many teachers report limited knowledge about ASD and struggle to identify behaviors linked to the condition, such as restricted and repetitive behaviors, making it challenging to manage students with ASD in mainstream classrooms (Welsh et al., 2019). Studies also suggest that teachers often misunderstand the nature of behaviors such as anxiety or sensory sensitivity, leading to less effective interventions (González et al., 2023). Furthermore, teachers who are more familiar with ASD or have received training are more likely to have positive attitudes and adopt appropriate strategies for managing ASD-related behaviors (Gómez-Marí et al., 2021). Unfortunately, many teachers feel unprepared to manage the emotional and behavioral challenges associated with ASD due to inadequate training and lack of support from school administrators

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(Simó-Pinatella et al., 2021). This gap in awareness extends to teachers' perceptions of students with ASD, where studies show that teachers' attitudes are shaped by misconceptions about the behaviors and needs of these students (Aysina et al., 2020). Teachers who are aware of a student's ASD diagnosis tend to perceive behaviors more positively, as diagnostic labels help them understand the behaviors as part of the condition, rather than as misbehavior (Nah & Tan, 2020). The awareness and attitudes of teachers are critical factors in providing inclusive education for children with ASD (Kofidou & Mantzikos, 2020).

While special education teachers are generally more knowledgeable about autism spectrum disorder (ASD) behaviors, general education teachers often report feeling less prepared to manage students with ASD effectively. Studies show that special education teachers are more likely to use evidence-based practices (EBPs) tailored to the needs of children with ASD, which helps mitigate challenging behaviors (Ramirez, 2023). In contrast, general education teachers often lack training in these practices and express a need for more support in managing ASD behaviors (Kocak & Sari, 2021). This disparity in preparedness is also evident in teachers' perceptions of challenging behaviors, such as restricted and repetitive behaviors, with general education teachers feeling less confident and more emotionally strained when dealing with these behaviors (Welsh et al., 2019). Moreover, research indicates that teachers' awareness and confidence in managing ASD behaviors are influenced by their previous experience with ASD students and the availability of training programs (Simó-Pinatella et al., 2021). Inadequate training and lack of ongoing professional development contribute to general education teachers feeling less equipped to address ASD-related challenges effectively (Singh, 2020). This gap in understanding and preparedness between general and special education teachers underscores the need for comprehensive training and professional support systems in both educational settings (Gómez-Marí et al., 2021).

Bridging the gap in knowledge and preparedness between general and special education teachers is crucial for creating a more inclusive educational environment for students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Research indicates that teachers who are better equipped with knowledge about ASD and its associated behaviors are more likely to implement inclusive strategies that benefit not only students with ASD but also their typically developing peers (Aysina et al., 2020). When teachers possess the necessary skills to manage challenging behaviors, students with ASD are more likely to engage in the learning process and experience improved academic and social outcomes (Nah, 2020). Inclusive education benefits all students by fostering a learning environment that values diversity and promotes understanding, which helps reduce stigma and enhances peer relationships (Lahodny et al., 2022). Closing the knowledge gap

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between general and special education teachers, schools can ensure that all students with ASD have access to quality education and the support they need to thrive academically and socially (González et al., 2023). The integration of evidence-based practices across both educational settings is key to achieving better outcomes for students with ASD (Ramírez, 2023).

The importance of this study lies in its potential to address critical gaps in teacher preparedness and awareness regarding the management of behaviors associated with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) in educational settings. As the prevalence of ASD continues to rise, more children with ASD are being integrated into mainstream classrooms, placing increasing demands on teachers to effectively support their diverse needs. This study aims to explore and compare the levels of awareness between general and special education teachers, offering insights into the disparities that exist and how they may impact the inclusivity and effectiveness of education for students with ASD. This research has the potential to inform teacher training programs, influence policy changes, and promote the development of more inclusive educational practices, ultimately leading to improved learning outcomes and a better school experience for students with ASD. Understanding how to equip teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge will be crucial in fostering an educational environment that supports the academic, social, and emotional well-being of all students.

Methodology

This study utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationship between the level of awareness of teachers regarding the behaviors of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and two key factors: the number of seminars and trainings attended and the number of years teaching children with ASD. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the respondents, which included 40 special education and general education teachers working in inclusive settings. These teachers were chosen based on their direct involvement in classrooms believed to include students with special needs. The study initially reached out to 46 potential participants, but only 40 completed questionnaires were retrieved. In addition to purposive sampling, complete enumeration was employed to ensure a thorough examination of the population. Data were collected using a researcher-made questionnaire, which was pilot-tested and validated by experts before distribution. The questionnaire was divided into three sections: respondent profiles, teacher awareness of ASD-related behaviors using a 4-point Likert scale, and challenges faced in teaching children with ASD. Data analysis included descriptive statistics to evaluate the level of awareness and a Pearson correlation coefficient to assess the

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relationships between teacher awareness and the number of seminars attended, as well as the number of years spent teaching children with ASD. This approach provided insights into the potential influence of professional experience and training on teachers' awareness of ASD behaviors.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Number of Years in teaching Children with Autism

Years in Teaching SPED	Frequency	Percentage (%)
25-29 years	1	2.50
20-24 years	0	0.00
15-19 years	0	0.00
10-14 years	3	7.50
5-9 years	5	12.50
4 years and below	31	77.50
Total	40	100.0

The data indicates that the majority of the teacher respondents (77.5%) have four years or less of experience in teaching children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), highlighting a concentration of relatively inexperienced educators in the field. Although some may possess theoretical knowledge about ASD, they are still in the process of fully immersing themselves in real-life classroom scenarios. Research by Gómez-Mari et al. (2021) supports the notion that educators with more years of experience working with ASD students have a deeper understanding of their needs and are better equipped to modify instruction. Teachers, especially those without specialized training in special education, may need to supplement their learning through self-study and practical experience. This aligns with the idea that experience is critical in developing effective teaching strategies for students with ASD. Moreover, studies suggest that institutional support and specialized training are essential in helping educators overcome challenges in inclusive classroom settings, further underscoring the importance of experience and professional development.

The data of table 2 reveals that 75% of respondents have attended 9 hours or less of seminars and trainings related to autism spectrum disorder (ASD), indicating limited formal exposure to ASD-specific professional development among most educators. A smaller portion of respondents (10%) has invested over 100 hours in training, suggesting a more dedicated group. The varying levels of training highlight a need for continued professional development to better equip teachers in handling students with ASD.

Table 2. Seminar and trainings Attended About Autism

Hours	Frequency	Percentage %
100 hours and above	4	10.00
90-99 hours	2	5.00
80-89 hours	0	0.00
70-79 hours	0	0.00
60-69 hours	2	5.00
50-59 hours	1	2.50
40-49 hours	0	0.00
30-39 hours	0	0.00
20-29 hours	0	0.00
10-19 hours	1	2.50
9 hours and below	30	75.00
Total	40	100.0

Research supports that teachers' self-efficacy and ability to work with autistic students improve significantly with increased training, emphasizing John Dewey's theory of "Learning by doing," where practical experience enhances the teaching process. Studies have consistently shown that real-world application of newly acquired skills through ongoing professional development is crucial for educators to effectively support students with ASD. Therefore, continued exposure to seminars and training is essential for teachers to stay updated with new strategies and best practices in special education.

Table 3. Level of Awareness of the Respondents on the Behavior of Child with Autism

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
Looks at you when s/he needs something.	2.68	0.89	Aware
Looks at you when you walk with her/him.	2.75	0.87	Aware
Uses her hand to point at something like a toy.	2.70	0.85	Aware
Uses facial expressions when happy, sad or angry.	2.63	0.95	Aware
Understands and reacts when you are angry, sad or happy.	2.58	0.98	Aware
Reacts when you show her/him a new toy or book.	2.60	0.93	Aware
Is overjoyed and when brought to a new place.	2.45	1.04	Moderately aware
Gets tantrums when she likes a food or toy	2.58	0.93	Aware
Displays mixed emotions when sad and angry.	2.63	0.95	Aware
Just nods head or give hand gesture to say no or yes.	2.43	1.01	Moderately aware
Does not show specific emotions.	2.45	0.90	Moderately aware
Does not look at others eyes (maintains gaze).	2.50	1.01	Moderately aware
Does not enjoy the presence of others.	2.55	0.96	Aware
Can communicate with others through body movement.	2.45	0.88	Moderately aware
Are non-verbal or limited speech development.	2.75	0.93	Aware
Over-talkative.	2.78	1.00	Aware
May lose the acquired speech	2.75	0.98	Aware
Show frequent movements of the hands and probably the body.	2.60	0.87	Aware
Very aggressive.	2.70	0.94	Aware
Very aggressive.	2.80	0.88	Aware
Defiant.	2.63	0.98	Aware
Non-compliant behavior.	2.68	1.00	Aware
Body rocking	2.75	1.01	Aware
Holding parts of the body in unusual position.	2.65	1.10	Aware
Biting arms, hitting, or other forms of self-injury.	2.73	1.06	Aware

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Repeating vocalization (for ex. "EEEEEE").	2.63	1.05	Aware
Heightened sensitivity or sensory aversion	2.73	1.04	Aware
Lack of interest in pretend play.	2.48	1.01	Moderately aware
Inspecting toys rather than playing with them.	2.60	0.98	Aware
Playing alone	2.58	1.01	Aware
Average Weighted Mean	2.63	0.97	Aware

The findings from Table 3 reveal that while the respondents demonstrate a moderate level of awareness (mean score of 2.63) regarding the behaviors of children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), there is still a gap in achieving full awareness. Key behaviors such as hyper-fixation and over-talkativeness are more commonly recognized, while behaviors like non-verbal communication and emotional cues are less understood. This highlights the need for further professional development and training to enhance teacher efficacy in supporting students with ASD, especially given that most respondents have limited experience. Research supports that additional training significantly improves teacher self-efficacy and promotes more effective inclusion of ASD students. Moreover, continuous education and awareness programs for educators are essential for fostering an inclusive learning environment and ensuring sustainable, high-quality education for children with special needs.

Table 4. Significant Relationship Between the Level of Awareness and the number of years of teaching Children with Autism and Seminars and Trainings Attended About Autism

Demographic Variable	Pearson Correlation (r)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Years of Teaching Autism	0.4595	0.0588	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Trainings Attended	0.8066	0.0006	Reject Ho	Significant

Significant ($p < 0.05$)

The correlation analysis reveals that the number of years teaching children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) has no significant impact on the level of teacher awareness regarding ASD behaviors, as indicated by a Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.4595 and a p -value of 0.0588. This suggests that even teachers with fewer years of experience can effectively understand ASD behaviors with proper training. However, the number of seminars and trainings attended about autism shows a significant positive relationship with awareness levels ($r = 0.8066$, $p = 0.0006$), emphasizing that professional development through relevant training substantially improves teacher awareness. These findings highlight the importance of continuous education and seminars to enhance teachers' capability to support children with ASD effectively, regardless of their years of teaching experience. Acharya & Baral (2023) in their study found out that there

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was no statistically significant correlation between the chosen background variables and the degree of ASD awareness. Moreover, findings indicate that less than 10% of respondents had a high degree of awareness about ASD, indicating that school teachers were not well-versed in the subject. It was indicated that ASD training was only received by one teacher. Teachers must therefore receive proper training and an awareness program on ASD in order to better understand the condition of autistic children and identify difficulties early on. As "broadcasting agents" of social changes and development, this will support educators in spreading knowledge about ASD in local communities.

Table 5. Problem Met in Handling Children with ASD

Problem Met in Handling Children with ASD	Frequency	Rank
Lack of support from the parents	35	1
Lack of support from the school administration.	35	1
Lack of instructional materials in teaching children with ASD.	35	1
Too many children with multiple disabilities in inclusive setting.	35	1
Budget problems.	32	2
Widespread misconception that teaching is easy.	29	3
The difficulty of discipline in a special needs classroom.	28	4
Handling problems in an inclusive classroom.	22	5
Professional isolation.	18	6
Non-instructional responsibilities.	18	7

The data from Table 5 reveals that the most significant challenges faced by teachers in handling children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) include a lack of support from parents and school administration, insufficient instructional materials, and the presence of many children with multiple disabilities in inclusive settings. These issues were reported by 35 respondents, ranking as the most critical concerns. Other notable challenges include budget constraints, misconceptions about the ease of teaching, difficulties in maintaining discipline, and handling inclusive classrooms. Additionally, some teachers reported professional isolation and non-instructional responsibilities as challenges. Overall, the findings highlight the need for better support, resources, and collaboration to effectively manage classrooms with children with ASD.

Conclusion

The findings indicate that while teachers demonstrate a moderate level of awareness regarding the behaviors of children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), significant gaps remain in their experience and professional development. The majority of respondents have limited years of experience teaching children with ASD and have attended few autism-related seminars or trainings, which significantly affects their

awareness levels. Despite this, many teachers are motivated to learn and support ASD students, though they face several challenges, including a lack of support from parents and school administration, insufficient instructional materials, budget constraints, and difficulties managing inclusive classrooms with multiple disabilities. These findings underscore the critical need for enhanced training, better resources, and stronger institutional support to improve the educational experience for both teachers and students in inclusive settings.

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